

122. The cosmic distance scale

THE CHALLENGES of establishing the cosmic distance scale has a long history extending back over many centuries. I will not say more about the situation pre-Hipparcos (1997), other than to note that, just 25 years ago, even the distance to the Hyades cluster, at a mere 46–47 pc, and one of the first ‘rungs’ on the distance ‘ladder’, was still not considered fully secure.

This changed with Hipparcos (e.g. Perryman et al., 1998), and with it the focus shifted to discussions of the distance to the Galactic centre (essay #111), and to the Large Magellanic Cloud (see figure on the next page).

At that time, the following ‘standard candles’ were used as luminosity calibrators to estimate the distance to the Large Magellanic Cloud:

- (a) Population I objects, including Cepheids, red clump giants, Mira variables, eclipsing binaries, SN 1987a, and main-sequence fitting (and turn-off). Cepheid methods were themselves subdivided into those based on trigonometric parallaxes, main-sequence fitting of open clusters, and the Baade–Wesselink method;
- (b) Population II objects, including subdwarf main-sequence fitting, horizontal branch parallaxes, RR Lyrae (pulsationally-unstable horizontal branch stars), globular cluster dynamics, and cooling sequences of white dwarfs in globular clusters. RR Lyrae were themselves subdivided into the use of statistical parallaxes, Baade–Wesselink method, and double-mode pulsators.

HIPPARCOS CONTRIBUTED to most of these, except those based on eclipsing binaries, SN 1987a, and globular cluster dynamics. Particular insight came from red clump giants, and globular cluster distances and age estimates from subdwarf main-sequence fitting.

Interpreting the literature can be confusing not least because of the various ‘paths’ that can be followed to get a distance estimate. Thus globular cluster distances can be determined from subdwarf main-sequence fitting, with those distances used to derive the absolute magnitude of RR Lyrae stars in that cluster, which are then applied as standard candles to the LMC. Or the RR Lyrae absolute magnitudes can be derived from statistical parallaxes of relatively nearby stars.

TODAY, as a result of advances in understanding the cosmic microwave background, the focus of attention has shifted to the different values of the Hubble constant, in the Λ CDM model, which have emerged from ‘early Universe’ techniques on the one hand, and ‘late Universe’ techniques on the other (see essay #44).

To recap, the former are based on measurements of the cosmic microwave background, viz. the ‘echo’ from the Big Bang that contains imprints of the Universe’s fundamental properties. Initially from NASA’s WMAP, and more recently from ESA’s Planck mission, the most recent Planck estimates yield $H_0 = 67.66 \pm 0.42 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (Aghanim et al., 2020).

The ‘late Universe’ methods rely on ‘distance ladders’: measuring the redshifts of distant galaxies, and then determining the distances to them by some other method. Two of these have been advanced by Gaia.

One uses the tip of the red-giant branch as a distance indicator, based on the fact that all red giants reach the same peak brightness at the end of their lives. The other is based on Cepheids, with Gaia EDR3 being the latest that I have seen used in the determination of H_0 .

A compilation by Verde et al. (2019), presented at the Kavli Institute workshop on the Hubble constant discrepancy, remains instructive: the various ‘late Universe’ results available at the time clearly had systematically larger error bars than the CMB-based results.

Perryman (2009; Figure 5.13)

AS NOTED by Clementini et al. (2020), the figure on the previous page suggests that the onus of improving the accuracy of H_0 would seem to fall on the ‘late Universe’ (distance ladder) methods, rather than the cosmic microwave background methods.

They argued that the improvement that Gaia should provide in the future should eventually allow H_0 be determined to $\sim 1\%$. They considered that this would be achieved through the following steps:

- detailed investigation of the systematics and zero-point offsets in EDR3 and later data releases [some of the various estimates of the Gaia catalogues’ zero-point offsets have been summarised by Lindegren (2020)];
- use of the Gaia parallaxes combined with near-infrared photometry for pulsating stars, to re-calibrate the Cepheid and RR Lyrae distance scales;
- the development of fine grids of nonlinear convective pulsation models for variable stars, in different evolutionary phases and in different environments, that should allow their dependence on physical and numerical assumptions to be examined;
- an improved treatment of population effects in Cepheids, RR Lyrae stars, Long-Period Variables, and the red giant branch, directly calibrated through more local Gaia parallaxes, all types being well represented in external systems such as the Large Magellanic Cloud;
- verification of the consistency between Population I and Population II distance scales in the Local Group;
- the investigation of alternative cosmic distance scale ‘anchors’, in addition to the traditionally adopted Large Magellanic Cloud, for example M31.

With this as the goal of the current approach to the cosmic distance ladder, in the process identifying reason(s) for the discrepancy between the early and late Universe estimates, it may well be some time before a clear consensus emerges. Meanwhile, I will look briefly at the associated work ongoing.

IN ADDITION TO the Gaia studies of Cepheids, mentioned in essays 43 and 44, and on RR Lyrae in essay 45, much work continues on understanding the zero-point and metallicity coefficients of the Cepheid period–luminosity relation, e.g., based on Gaia EDR3 (Ripepi et al., 2021; De Somma et al., 2022; Molinaro et al., 2023), and later on Gaia DR3 (Breuval et al., 2022).

Other efforts to improve the understanding and calibration of the tip of the red giant branch population (a population II standard candle related to the helium flash in low mass stars) have been made with EDR3 and DR3 (e.g. Soltis et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022), with Mould et al. (2019) suggesting that, as the mission proceeds, ‘... *there is every reason to think that an accurate Galactic geometric calibration of tip of the red giant branch will be a significant outcome for the extragalactic distance scale*’.

On the other hand, recent work using Type II supernovae, rather than Type Ia, yields results consistent with other local measurements, with no indication that Type Ia supernovae or Cepheids could be the source of the current ‘ H_0 tension’ (de Jaeger et al., 2022).

OTHER CLASSES of object may also be able to contribute to the debate. Chen et al. (2018) demonstrated a tight (orbital) period–luminosity relation in 183 nearby W UMA-type contact binary systems with early Tycho–Gaia parallaxes, and identifying 27 000 that could eventually yield accurate distances within 3 kpc.

And various other studies, based on Gaia distances, are investigating the use of the central stars of planetary nebulae as a class of standard candle, including Stanghellini et al. (2020) using Gaia DR2, and Ali et al. (2022) using Gaia EDR3.

WHILE WE WAIT for the next advances in understanding the cosmic distance scale with Gaia, a readable account of the subject’s history, and the role of space astrometry, has been given by Mignard (2019).